

Completed projects	Main objectives	Actions	Expected impacts
NYM0221	The overarching objective for the farm is to produce 100% grass fed Beef to sell direct to the general public A conservation grazing approach will be used to enhance grassland habitats	Installing a portable water supply trough and pipe Installing rabbit fencing to protect drilled herbal lay from rabbits Water trough	Enhance grassland habitats Store water and carbon Improve soil conditions Reduce flood risk Landscape more resilient to climate change Wildlife rich habitat Improve the production and profitability of the business
NYM0321	The project will provide business skills Financial recording training	Workshop material development	To ensure that farming businesses are prepared To ensure that they hold the necessary basic business and financial recording skills
NYM0121	Increase soil organic matter Increase carbon sequestration Reduce Runoff Introduce companion Cropping Introduce more cover Cropping Reduce artificial nutrient and Plant protection products applied Improve farm resilience through increased access to ELS	High technology 4 metre direct drill	Regenerative farming approach Increase soil organic matter Sequester more carbon Reduce runoff Reduce the use of artificial Nitrogen, herbicides and Pesticides Reduce weed burden and herbicide use Benefit from no-till practices Reduce soil erosion Prevents pollution from entering nearby water sources Provide cover and food for birds and other species

			<p>Flood risk reduced</p> <p>Land being more resilient to climate change</p> <p>Increased farm business resilience (contract drilling for other farmers)</p>
NYM0421	<p>To harvest the natural rainwater</p> <p>A reduction in localised flooding</p> <p>Provide a useful resource for a farm</p>	<p>Rainwater storage tanks</p> <p>First flush rainwater diverters and downpipe filters</p>	<p>To reduce flooding risk the stored rainwater water during the summer months for arable operations and general farm use.</p> <p>Less diffuse pollution entering the watercourse</p> <p>Reducing flash flooding also contributes to protection of infrastructure</p> <p>Improve bathing water quality</p>
NYM0521	<p>Fencing off to prevent livestock from accessing</p> <p>To protect trees and stop soil erosion</p> <p>To protect sediment ending up in water course</p>	<p>Sheep netting</p> <p>Fencing supplement - difficult sites</p> <p>Wooden field gate</p>	<p>Cleaner water and stopping land erosion</p> <p>Protecting areas for nature to flourish</p> <p>health and well-being of the cattle stopping them getting trapped in the dense woodland</p> <p>Promote land management to sustain and enhance biodiversity</p> <p>Cultural heritage</p> <p>Help farmers to improve the production and profitability of their businesses</p>
NYM0921	<p>To ensure that the building stock within the National Park is conserved in good condition</p>	<p>North York Moors NT Condition Surveys</p>	<p>Improved planning and better value for money when conducting conservation, repair and maintenance</p>

Quantify any backlog of repairs
 Plan future conservation and maintenance of farm buildings
 Support and inform a future Conservation Management Plan

To improve the condition of our building stock within the historic landscapes

National Trust's records

NYM1121	To improve the accessibility of the public Provision of gates and stiles	Stile Kits Dog Latch kits Gates of various sizes Gate Posts Metalwork Fencing Material	Volunteer engagement Improved public access
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NYM1221	To provide fencing and associated infrastructure to allow cattle to restoratively graze 33.06 hectare area of Caydale SSSI (Natural England) Gates for access Nectar, food and shelter for invertebrates To attract birds and increase ground-nesting	permanent fencing Difficult site fencing supplement Wooden Gates	Carbon stored Farm business mre environmentally sustainable enhance biodiversity Increase soil organic matter levels To increased rainwater storage Understanding and Enjoyment
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NYM1421	Hedge planting Protective fencing	Hedge planting Stock fencing	Ensuring water course is stack proof
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NYM1321	Restoration of traditional stone wall boundaries Contribution towards equipment that will help control pollution	Rowantree fields wall restoration Gate post Gate Slidney Beck wall restoration Yard Brush and Bucket	Pollution control Improved landscape quality Better management of existing habitats
NYM1821	To enhance the surface of the dismantled railway line	Drainage and surface construction	To provide a pleasant walking and riding experience To provide a more durable surface at the weakest points To prevent damage and access issues People enjoying the route
NYM1921	Putting concrete to a main patio to reduce pollution Health of the cattle Stopping sediments and gravel	Concrete yard	Favourable working environment Protecting the river for pollution Improved conditions of wildlife and watercourses Improved oxygen levels of the water
NYM2321	To reduce slurry To reduce dirty water To reduce the amount of run off from the yard To diversify the business To improve an existing boundary fence To further reduce run-off and pollution on the farm by doubling our rainwater collection	Hedgerow gapping up Farm Shop Vending Machine Steel shed to cover feed area Rainwater harvesting tank Associated pipework and filters for rainwater collection	Reduced run-off and water collection to create good habitat for wildlife To help capture carbon Increase biodiversity Improve the quality of water bodies to store rainwater Improve bathing water quality Help farmers to improve the production and profitability of their businesses
NYM2521	To exclude stock	Stock netting	New wildlife habitats

To create an area of pollinator friendly species
 To increase connectivity between habitats
 To sequester carbon
 To reduce the carbon footprint
 To replace trees
 To create an area for visitors and users

Enhance visitor experiences

Natural regeneration

Wildlife corridors

NYM2621

To improve the ancient footpaths
 To create a wood pasture habitat with tussocky grassland
 Trees
 To create a perfect habitat for invertebrates
 To provide small mammal habitat
 The fruiting tree species will benefit birds.
 To provide a food source for many other species

Planting standard parkland tree

Supply and plant tree

Tree guard (wood post and wire)

Access improvement

Improved public access

Habitat connection

To protect and enhance the landscape as a whole

To sustain and enhance biodiversity

Cultural heritage

To increase the number of people visiting the National Park

To improve their health and wellbeing

To connect with nature

Understand the special qualities of the National Park

NYM2721

Bank stabilisation on the Murk Esk
 Training of NYMNPA Volunteers

Gloves

High vis builders line

Hammers

To prevent future erosion of the river bank

To prevent the mobilisation of fine sediment into the downstream environment

To protect a public right of way running

To create a baseline from which restoration work can commence

Metal fencing pins
Dry stone walling courses

NYM2821

To reduce slurry production
To reduce the chance of dirty water entering water courses

Feed yard roof

To enhance the SSSI grassland
Protect and enhance the landscape as a whole
Promote land management to sustain and enhance biodiversity
Improve the quality of water bodies
Improve bathing water quality
Understanding and enjoyment
Improve the quality and variety of facilities for visitors
Help farmers to improve the production and profitability of their businesses

To move from slurry to a Farm Yard Manure (FYM) system

To increase biodiversity on the farm

Reduced grazing density
Removing livestock over winter

To create wildlife corridors and foraging areas

To provide educational access
Reducing animal and sediment inputs

To reduce run-off entering Tranmire Slack Beck

To reduce the rainwater which has to be stored

To increase organic matter

NYM2121

To conserve historic features
To enhance quality and character of the landscape
Dry stone wall restoration

Rebuild dry stone wall

Better management of habitats
Enhanced landscapes
Conservation of historic features

NYM1122	To create a wildlife corridor disabilities To provide work opportunities to adults with learning desabilities who live in the NYMNP	Trees Shelters	Enhance biodiversity Habitat connectivity Carbon sequestered Water retention Green jobs Health and wellbeing Nature connection
NYM0522	To reduce the carbon footprint of the farm To reduce the environmental impact of the farm To install a rainwater harvesting system To improve farm resilience	Slurry bag Water tank Soil water pipe Rainwater diverters Wash down water pump kit	To reduce the use of fertilizer 70% Improved farm resilience Increased soil carbon Increased soil water storage Nutrient retention Increased soil biodiversity To reduce pollution to water course To benefit the economics of the farming business To protect and enhance the landscape as a whole
NYM4121	To combine cutting of heather with traditional burning methods to improve the habitat condition To reduce the risk of wild fire To reduce the encroachment of bracken and scrub onto the heathland	Griffith JB 600 jungle buster	Enhance biodiversity Understanding and Enjoyment Business and Land Management To support the sustainable management of moorland
NYM3721	To increase connectivity between habitats	Sheep netting	To increase flora and fauna biodiversity on the farm

	<p>To increase biodiversity</p> <p>To create habitats for pollinators</p> <p>To increase the amount of carbon sequestration</p> <p>Planting native hedgerow trees</p> <p>To provide nectar for pollinators and fruit for birds</p> <p>Shelter and safe passage to small mammals</p> <p>Nesting opportunities for small birds</p> <p>To create insect pathways</p>	<p>Supplement for use of individual tree-shelters</p> <p>Planting new hedges</p> <p>Planting standard hedgerow tree</p> <p>Wooden field gate</p>	<p>To create a new wildlife corridor</p> <p>Habitat connectivity</p> <p>Enhance biodiversity</p> <p>Understanding and Enjoyment</p> <p>Enhancing the experience of visitors to the area</p> <p>To improve production and profitability of the businesses</p>
NYM3421	<p>Improving access for the public</p> <p>Protecting landscape between the moor and the sea</p> <p>Protection of new wild flower meadow</p>	<p>Fencing</p>	<p>Stock proof fencing will prevent further damage</p> <p>To prevent footfall over the heather and the meadow</p> <p>Better management of existing habitats</p> <p>Greater understanding and enjoyment of the landscape</p>
NYM1922	<p>106 metres of native hedge to be planted</p> <p>To protect the new hedge from livestock</p>	<p>Hedgerow creation</p>	<p>Improved connectivity between habitats</p> <p>Carbon sequestered</p> <p>Increased of biodiversity</p> <p>Enhanced landscape</p>
NYM2622	<p>To fence off a wildlife corridor including the watercourse</p>	<p>Fencing</p> <p>Livestock Trough</p> <p>Associated Pipework</p>	<p>Wildlife corridor</p> <p>to protect the current levels of biodiversity</p> <p>Reducing the risk of pollutants entering the watercourse</p> <p>enhancing and protecting the landscape and biodiversity</p>

			To improve the quality of the watercourse Excluding livestock
NYM2722	The bridge's repair and for the reopening of the public right of way To improve their health and well-being To connect with nature	Bridge repair	Opportunities for people to explore, enjoy and understand the landscape Nature connection Health and wellbeing Improved public access
NYM2921	To rejuvenate the existing hedge and add more diverse hedge species To provide an early pollen source Enhance the connectivity on the farm to benefit biodiversity The archaeological and built heritage will be conserved Better wildlife connectivity	Hedge-laying Hedge Gapping Double fencing Walling Top-wiring of wall	Sequester carbon Enhance soil health To protect the heritage of the farm To protect the landscape of the NYMNP Volunteer engagement Knowledge and understanding of the archaeological and built heritage Existing habitats will be conserved, restored and expanded Habitat connectivity Wildlife corridor Enhance Biodiversity
NYM0422	Repair stone wall	Stone wall restoration x 200m	Maintenance of landscape character and features Maintain the conservation benefits of adjoining ancient and semi natural wood Enhanced enjoyment by the public Increase engagement by the public
NYM2222	To fence off river and woodland	Clipex posts	There will be a greater protection and an increase in local wildlife.

	To prevent livestock from poaching and damaging the trees	Strainers Wire Barbed Wire Rails	To allow new life and young saplings to regenerate
NYM2422	Establishment of wildlife plot To establish a winter bird food and pollinator mix To sow a diverse range of crops for wildlife benefit	Ploughing Power harrowing Broadcasting seed Harrow in seed Rolling Seeds	Wildlife will benefit from the pollen and nectar resources Winter seed source To protect and enhance the landscape as a whole Promote land management to sustain and enhance biodiversity To connect with nature
NYM4222	Catchment-scale restoration project To improve the ecological and chemical status of watercourses and habitat extent. New woodland, buffer strips, hedge-planting and grassland restoration Connect habitats New woodland, wood pasture, hedgerows and grass margins Catchment-scale restoration	EA match funding Fencing Wooden field-gates Livestock troughs Trees Watercourse crossing In-field tree guard Tree surgery Hedge-planting Species-rich grassland Buffer strip Pond creation Wetland creation Leaky dams	To improve carbon storage Reduced flood risk Better understanding of habitat type To sequester carbon Create, expand and connect habitats Biodiversity gain Managing existing habitats under better conditions To enjoy and understand the landscape volunteer assistance Improved landscape character Habitat creation/expansion Improved sustainable farm business models Water-quality Creation and expansion of habitats, operating at a catchment scale